

Advancing Educational Equity through Sustainable AI Deployment: Strategies and Innovations for the United Kingdom

Okunola Orogun ✉

*Premby inc, Washington DC, USA
Global Banking School, United Kingdom*

Lanre Ogungbe

Premby inc, Washington DC, USA

Ayodeji Ajani

Global Banking School, United Kingdom

Niyi Adegboye

Premby inc, Washington DC, USA

Omotayo Ogunsola

Lamar University, USA

Abstract

Enhancing educational fairness is a cornerstone of a just society, ensuring equal opportunities for all individuals, regardless of their background. Achieving equity in education involves providing necessary support to level the playing field for everyone. This paper examines the significance of educational equity in the context of the United Kingdom, particularly highlighted by the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic exacerbated existing inequalities, particularly affecting vulnerable students and those with special educational needs. The study underscores the moral and strategic imperatives of addressing these disparities to foster social unity, economic prosperity, and sustainable development. The paper delves into socioeconomic disparities as a major obstacle to educational fairness, illustrating how children from underprivileged backgrounds face significant barriers to accessing quality education. These inequalities perpetuate cycles of poverty and hinder social mobility. The study also explores the correlation between socioeconomic status and educational attainment, offering insights into the persistent challenges and necessary collaborative efforts to promote educational equity in the UK.

Keywords: *Educational Equity, Sustainable development, Artificial Intelligence, UK education.*

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Introduction

Promoting educational fairness serves as a fundamental principle in any society striving for justice and progress. It ensures that every individual, irrespective of their background or circumstances, has an equal chance to realize their potential through schooling. Equity, often likened to "leveling the playing field," is attained when everyone receives the necessary support to be on par with others in the same educational environment. According to the Glossary of Education Reform, equity is synonymous with fairness, yet it acknowledges the various ways unfair policies and practices can perpetuate inequality, leading to unequal educational performance and outcomes. The COVID-19 pandemic's impact on secondary education underscores the significance of equity in schooling. A report by the OECD in 2020 revealed that over 188 countries, covering approximately 91% of enrolled students globally, shut down schools to curb the virus's spread. Highlighting the issue, the OECD referenced a UK study indicating that a significant portion of vulnerable students and those with special educational needs (SEN) were less engaged in remote learning compared to their peers. In the United Kingdom, the pursuit of educational equity is not just a moral obligation but also a strategic imperative for fostering social unity, economic prosperity, and sustainable development. The following section emphasizes the diverse benefits and the urgent need for collaborative efforts to address discrepancies in access, academic achievement, and educational outcomes throughout the education system.

Socioeconomic Disparities

In the UK, one of the most prominent obstacles to achieving educational fairness arises from socioeconomic disparities. Children from underprivileged backgrounds frequently encounter hurdles in accessing quality education due to insufficient resources, inadequate facilities, and limited enrichment opportunities. These inequalities sustain cycles of poverty and social marginalization, impeding upward social mobility and perpetuating inequities across generations. The study by Broer et al. (2019) explores the socioeconomic status (SES) and its associated factors, examining the correlation between SES and educational attainment, as well as disparities among educational systems and shifts over time.

According to Mulis et al. (2016), the link between family background and children's academic performance is universally acknowledged. However, the strength of this correlation varies depending on the social environment and the education framework in place. Essentially, in education systems characterized by heightened overall inequality, such as income disparities, the achievement gap between students from diverse backgrounds is more pronounced. While most education systems aim to narrow this gap, it's crucial to recognize that stagnant scores among low-SES students and declining scores among high-SES students do not signify progress toward equality. Instead, educational systems should strive for equity by enhancing the performance of all students, with a specific focus on accelerating progress among low-SES students to diminish disparities in academic achievement. Prioritizing educational fairness in the UK can disrupt these cycles, unleashing the full potential of every child and ensuring that success is determined by talent rather than socioeconomic background.

Ethnic and Racial Disparities

Ethnic and racial disparities represent a significant aspect of educational equity challenges in the UK. Minority ethnic groups, such as Black, Asian, and minority ethnic (BAME) communities, often encounter disproportionate levels of educational disadvantage due to various barriers, including discrimination, cultural biases, and systemic inequalities. According to data from the Higher Education Statistics Agency (2023), the majority of individuals starting undergraduate study in the 2019-2020 academic year were White (72.6%), with smaller percentages representing Asian (12.2%), Black (8.7%), Mixed ethnicity (4.5%), and other ethnic groups (2.0%). This data tracks the enrolment of students in full-time and part-time undergraduate and postgraduate programs in the UK by ethnicity. In a study by Leon (2022), an analysis and critique of the education component of the 2021 Sewell Report on Race and Ethnic Disparities is presented. The critique highlights the report's purported objectivity, its failure to address racism, and the inadequacy of its recommendations. Drawing on Omi and Winant's concept of racial formation, the analysis interprets the Sewell report as part of a broader hegemonic effort to redefine British identity amid deepening crises of capitalism. It examines the report within the context of three racial projects — nationalist, multicultural, and antiracist — and argues that it aligns with a nationalist agenda, despite flaws. The study concludes by proposing a progressive approach to advancing racial and cultural justice.

Additionally, findings from Guerrero (2022) indicate that ethnic minority students face challenges including limited access to technology, insufficient support for child-care responsibilities, lack of peer interactions, and inadequate institutional support for mental well-being. However, inclusive support services and welcoming learning environments, including peer-to-peer learning spaces, are identified as facilitators of effective learning and emotional well-being. The study underscores persistent inequalities in access, support, and well-being in higher education and advocates for equitable access and support provision for ethnic minorities to enable all students to reach their full potential. To address these disparities, proactive measures are needed to promote inclusive and culturally responsive education, celebrate diversity, and dismantle institutional barriers. By embracing diversity and creating inclusive learning environments, the UK can harness the talents and contributions of all its citizens, fostering social cohesion and national unity.

Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND)

Educational equity extends to meeting the diverse requirements of learners with disabilities and special educational needs (SEN). Despite legal safeguards and policy frameworks aimed at fostering inclusive education, many children and youth with SEND encounter obstacles in accessing appropriate support and accommodations. In the Special Educational Needs Code of Practice for Wales (2002), the Minister for Education and Lifelong Learning articulated the role of the SEN Code of Practice in enhancing the educational journey of children with special educational needs, regardless of whether they have a formal statement. Emphasizing the vision of Wales as a Learning Country, the Minister underscored the Code's objective of eliminating barriers to participation and learning, with a central tenet being the provision of tailored support to meet the needs of children with SEN. Offering effective assistance to children with special educational needs stands as a fundamental aspect of effective educational institutions. The Code aims to provide clearer guidance for early years providers, primary and secondary school educators, local education authorities, families, and all stakeholders involved in catering to children's special educational

requirements. Enhancing educational equity for learners with SEND necessitates investments in inclusive teaching methodologies, targeted support services, and the cultivation of a culture characterized by respect, dignity, and empowerment. By recognizing and appreciating the unique capabilities and contributions of each learner, the UK can establish a more inclusive and equitable educational framework that ensures no one is left behind.

Global Competitiveness and Innovation

Apart from its inherent importance, educational equity plays a vital role in bolstering the UK's international competitiveness and fostering innovation. Globalization offers access to diverse knowledge sources, perspectives, and experiences from across the globe. A diverse and inclusive educational system nurtures creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities, providing individuals with the skills necessary to thrive in an ever-changing global landscape. In the study conducted by Chentukov et al. (2021), which focuses on the educational determinants shaping the socioeconomic development of countries worldwide, including an examination of the impact of national higher education system development indicators on economic development, macroeconomic factors, innovation, and technology, the findings reveal significant correlations. The level of competitiveness in higher education is closely linked with indicators such as global innovation development (0.8 between 2012-2020), knowledge intensity of GDP (0.73), and socioeconomic development (0.75). These findings enable the consideration of changes in educational indicators within the context of their influence on economic and global development strategies. By leveraging the talents of all individuals, regardless of their background or circumstances, the UK can unlock untapped potential, stimulate economic expansion, and establish itself as a global frontrunner in education, research, and innovation.

Educational equity stands as both a moral imperative and a strategic necessity for the United Kingdom. Prioritizing equity in education is not only about building a fairer and more inclusive society but also about unlocking the full potential of all citizens and securing a brighter future for generations to come. Embracing diversity, dismantling barriers, and fostering inclusive learning environments are crucial steps toward realizing the vision of educational equity in the UK. The educational landscape of the United Kingdom confronts various challenges, including disparities in access and attainment, as well as evolving pedagogical needs in an increasingly digital era. Amidst this dynamic environment, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerges as a transformative tool with the potential to revolutionize teaching, learning, and administrative processes. AI presents a unique opportunity to address longstanding educational challenges, enhance equity and inclusion, and prepare students for success in the 21st century. Its transformative potential lies in its capacity to analyze vast datasets, identify patterns, and deliver personalized learning experiences tailored to individual needs and preferences. By harnessing machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics, AI can adjust instruction in real-time, offering targeted support to struggling students and challenging high achievers to reach their full potential.

This personalized approach not only fosters academic growth but also promotes equity by addressing the diverse learning needs of students from varying backgrounds and abilities. Additionally, AI-powered educational technologies have the potential to democratize access to quality education, overcoming barriers of geography, socioeconomic status, and physical limitations. Virtual learning environments, intelligent tutoring systems, and educational apps powered by AI enable learners to access educational resources anytime, anywhere, thereby leveling the playing field and

expanding educational opportunities for all. Beyond personalized learning, AI holds promise in enhancing administrative efficiency and resource allocation within the UK educational system. AI-driven tools for data analysis, student assessment, and administrative tasks streamline workflows, optimize resource allocation, and empower educators and policymakers to make data-informed decisions. By automating routine tasks and equipping educators with actionable insights, AI liberates valuable time and resources that can be reinvested in supporting student learning and well-being.

The January 2024 report from the UK Parliament, "*Use of artificial intelligence in education delivery and assessment*," offers profound insights into this emerging paradigm. The report underscores AI's rapid development, particularly generative AI, which now enables the creation of realistic texts, images, audio, and videos. This technological leap forwards the possibility of varied learning methodologies and the automation of traditional educational tasks. Gen AI's potential to revolutionize lesson planning and grading is immense, setting the stage for a future where educators can dedicate more time to fostering deeper learning and student engagement. With an investment of up to £2 million for AI-powered resources in England, there's a strong belief in AI's ability to improve learning outcomes. A pivotal point raised in this report is the need to address inequalities in AI tool access. Ensuring equitable access to the benefits of AI advancements is crucial to preventing the widening of the digital divide. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, a study conducted by the Sutton Trust (2021) highlighted concerning findings. In the first week of the January 2021 lockdown, 17% of teachers in the UK reported that one in five of their students lacked access to a device for remote learning. This gap was particularly stark between state and private schools, as only 5% of teachers in state schools indicated that all their students possessed the necessary devices for remote education, compared to 54% of teachers in private schools who reported that their students had sufficient access to such devices.

Nevertheless, unlocking AI's transformative capabilities in education necessitates thoughtful deliberation regarding ethical, privacy, and equity concerns. Prioritizing the protection of data privacy, addressing biases in algorithms, and ensuring fair access to AI-driven resources are essential for cultivating trust and promoting inclusivity within the educational sphere. By harnessing AI's potential to tailor learning experiences, broaden access, and improve administrative processes, the UK can construct a more equitable, inclusive, and efficient education system that equips all students for success in an ever-evolving digital landscape.

This paper seeks to review the current educational landscape in the UK with emphasis but not limited to all the disparities to education equity and digital divide, review existing literatures on AI tools used highlighting the potential of advancing sustainable AI in UK education, evaluate the impact of AI tools on educational equity and proffer recommendations for sustainable AI deployment to address educational equity in UK. The objective of this study is to explore the potential implications of AI integration in UK education by conducting a comprehensive review and thematic analysis of existing literature within three primary domains: applications, strategies, and effects. The review primarily examines the utilization of artificial intelligence in collaborative teacher-student learning, intelligent tutoring systems, automated assessment, and personalized learning.

Background and Significance

Overview of the Current Educational Landscape in the UK

The United Kingdom (UK) boasts a rich and diverse educational landscape that reflects its commitment to providing accessible and high-quality education for all. However, within this landscape, there exist notable disparities that impact various aspects of the educational experience, from early childhood education to higher education attainment.

Early Years Education

In the realm of early childhood education, the UK has made notable advancements in offering fundamental learning experiences for children from birth to five years old. Initiatives such as free nursery education across England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland are designed to guarantee that every child has access to high-quality early learning opportunities, laying a solid foundation for their future endeavours. However, disparities exist in access to early years education, with socio-economic factors often influencing a child's ability to access these programs. Children from disadvantaged backgrounds may face barriers to accessing quality early education, leading to disparities in school readiness and long-term educational outcomes.

Primary Education

Primary education in the UK provides essential building blocks for future academic success, covering nursery, infant, and junior stages. While the UK's primary education system aims to provide a comprehensive curriculum and supportive learning environment for all students, disparities persist in terms of educational outcomes and attainment. Various factors, including socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and geographical location, can profoundly influence a child's educational journey and results. For instance, children from underprivileged backgrounds may encounter obstacles like restricted access to resources, inferior school quality, and heightened levels of educational disparity, resulting in gaps in academic performance and advancement.

Secondary Education

In secondary education, students in the UK transition to more specialized learning pathways, including comprehensive schools, grammar schools, and academies. While the UK's secondary education system offers diverse pathways for students to pursue their educational goals, disparities exist in terms of access to high-quality educational opportunities and resources. Individuals hailing from less privileged backgrounds may encounter obstacles like restricted entry to advanced coursework, extracurricular engagements, and guidance counselling, thereby resulting in discrepancies in academic achievements and post-secondary prospects.

Higher Education

In higher education, the UK offers a wide range of academic and vocational courses, including undergraduate and postgraduate degrees. While higher education in the UK aims to provide opportunities for individuals to pursue their academic and career aspirations, disparities exist in terms of access, attainment, and progression. Factors such as socio-economic background, ethnicity, and prior educational experiences can impact a student's ability to access and succeed in higher education. Additionally, disparities in student support services, financial aid, and academic advising can further exacerbate inequalities in higher education attainment and outcomes.

Current Disparities Landscape in UK

Despite ongoing efforts to advance educational equity in the UK through various interventions, the issue of educational disadvantage remains persistent. According to UCAS (2023), students from the least advantaged backgrounds have only a 2 in 100 chance of attending the most competitive universities, in stark contrast to 28 in 100 for their most advantaged counterparts. This glaring disparity implies that less advantaged students are nearly 14 times more likely to be excluded from university education. Moreover, the situation is growing increasingly challenging, with a rising number of children experiencing economic hardship, resulting in heightened food insecurity both at home and in school. This predicament not only impacts their immediate well-being but also holds profound implications for their educational achievements and prospects. Presently, an alarming 3 million pupils, accounting for approximately 1 in 4 pupils in England, qualify for Free School Meals—a trend observed across all local authorities. These figures underscore the harsh reality of food insecurity and inequality within the education system. Access to nutritious meals is pivotal for a child's academic advancement: ensuring they are adequately nourished and comfortable in the classroom enables them to concentrate, participate in discussions, and sustain the energy necessary for contemplating their future aspirations. Acknowledging the diverse reasons behind a child's lack of concentration or disengagement, it is imperative for the education sector to address food insecurity as a significant barrier to academic success.

The gap in academic achievement between the most privileged and least privileged students has reached unprecedented levels. According to the National Foundation for Educational Research (NFER) in 2022, students eligible for free school meals at Key Stage 2 (KS2) lag behind their more advantaged peers by 7 months. By the time they reach GCSE level, this discrepancy widens to 18 months. In Wales, the gap is even more pronounced, standing at approximately 22-23 months. Moreover, students experiencing persistent poverty face even greater academic hurdles: in England, the persistent disadvantage gap equates to about 23 months of learning, while in Wales, it rises to 29 months. On average, students eligible for free school meals achieve over three quarters of a grade lower per GCSE subject compared to their peers from more affluent backgrounds.

The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these disparities, with annual gaps in academic achievement widening. Even among less privileged students who excel academically, their confidence in their abilities is severely diminished. According to research by The Sutton Trust in 2023, following the pandemic, 21% of disadvantaged high achievers express a lack of optimism about their prospects. This underscores the significance of self-efficacy – a student's belief in their capacity and competence to pursue their aspirations – in shaping later life outcomes. For instance, the same study found that disadvantaged students with high academic performance were 10% less likely to envision themselves pursuing further studies in two years' time compared to their more advantaged counterparts. Moreover, financial constraints increasingly hinder the prospect of attending university, despite students having the necessary qualifications. For instance, findings from the COSMO Study in 2023 reveal that 27% of students from working-class backgrounds and 39% of those who have relied on food banks in the past year express reluctance to apply to university due to financial constraints, compared to 19% of students from professional or managerial families. Additionally, 39% of students from families utilizing food banks express concerns about the affordability of university education. Furthermore, less privileged students

aspiring to attend university are more likely to reside with their families during their academic pursuits, as highlighted in the COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities Study of 2023. With the escalating costs of rent and food, compounded by maintenance grants failing to keep pace with inflation, many students are already grappling with the challenge of securing affordable accommodation upon commencing university studies in September.

Potential of AI in education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) stands poised to transform education by tailoring learning experiences, boosting accessibility, and streamlining administrative tasks. Worldwide, numerous instances underscore AI's revolutionary impact on education. A notable case is the utilization of AI-driven adaptive learning platforms like Docebo, Absorb LMS, LearnUpon, EdApp, and Cornerstone, among others. These platforms analyze student data to furnish customized learning paths adapted to individual needs and learning styles. For example, Khan Academy employs AI algorithms to furnish personalized learning experiences, enabling students to advance at their own pace and receive targeted assistance in challenging areas. Another arena witnessing significant AI advancements is language learning. AI-driven language learning applications such as Duolingo and Babbel leverage natural language processing algorithms to deliver interactive and personalized language instruction. These apps adjust to each learner's skill level and learning preferences, facilitating more efficient language acquisition.

Furthermore, AI is enhancing accessibility in education. AI-powered assistive technologies like speech recognition software and text-to-speech applications empower students with disabilities to participate more fully in learning activities. These technologies help level the educational landscape for students with diverse learning requirements, empowering them to actively engage in the learning process. In addition to improving learning outcomes, AI is streamlining administrative tasks in education. Educational institutions are leveraging AI-powered tools for tasks such as student enrolment, scheduling, and grading. For example, Chatbots equipped with natural language processing capabilities are being used to handle student inquiries and provide real-time support, reducing administrative burden on staff. Furthermore, AI is playing a crucial role in enhancing educational research and development. Researchers are using AI algorithms to analyse large datasets and identify patterns in learning behaviour, which can inform the design of more effective teaching strategies and curriculum development.

While these international examples illustrate the vast possibilities of AI in education, it's crucial to acknowledge the ethical concerns and hurdles linked with its adoption. Matters like data privacy, algorithmic bias, and bridging the digital divide require attention to guarantee fair access to AI-driven educational tools and chances for all students. Nevertheless, through diligent reflection and conscientious deployment, AI holds the promise to revolutionize education and empower learners on a global scale.

Literature Review

Existing Research on AI Applications in Education

In the educational landscape, a persistent challenge confronting educators and policymakers alike is the academic achievement gap. This disparity reflects the substantial variance in educational performance between students from more privileged socioeconomic backgrounds and those from less advantaged ones. A study

funded by the Nuffield Foundation and conducted by the IFS, as reported in 2022, uncovered significant insights from data collected from schools across the UK. The results revealed that fewer than half of students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds, as identified by eligibility for free school meals, had attained expected academic standards by the end of primary school. Conversely, approximately 70% of students from more affluent families had achieved similar levels of proficiency. Similarly, secondary school data mirrored this trend: only 40% of disadvantaged students obtained satisfactory GCSE results in core subjects like Mathematics and English, compared to 60% of their peers from more privileged backgrounds.

While this pattern is not exclusive to the UK and has been observed in education systems globally to varying extents, it highlights a systemic issue contributing to socioeconomic inequality. Despite concerted efforts through policy interventions and community-driven initiatives, the achievement gap persists, exacerbating existing social divides between economic classes. The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic further magnified this gap as students grappled with remote learning from home. This underscored the significant impact of a student's home environment on their academic performance and highlighted the limitations of digital technology in bridging educational disparities for disadvantaged students. As the future of education increasingly embraces digital learning modalities and remote study options, there is a risk of widening the attainment gap unless proactive measures are implemented to ensure equitable access to digital learning resources both within the home and educational institutions.

Personalised Learning Experience

Access to personalized learning is a critical advantage that students from affluent backgrounds often enjoy, giving them an edge over their peers. Wealthier families can afford private schooling, where smaller class sizes allow for more individualized attention from teachers. Additionally, private tutoring, which has traditionally been accessible only to wealthier families, further enhances a child's academic performance. In the UK, efforts have been made to extend personalized learning opportunities to less privileged students. Numerous private schools extend scholarships and bursaries to gifted students from low-income households, while state schools and community learning centers administer after-school clubs aimed at delivering tailored assistance and learning opportunities to disadvantaged students. However, these endeavours frequently encounter obstacles like inadequate funding and limited efficacy in bridging the achievement divide. Scholarship programs, for instance, often function more as avenues for identifying talent rather than addressing educational disparities. Furthermore, after-school clubs may not adequately substitute for the quality support provided by private tutoring, particularly in economically disadvantaged areas where resource limitations lead to a deterioration in their standard. Despite these challenges, evidence underscores the importance of making personalized learning accessible to students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds as pivotal for narrowing the achievement gap.

In 2020, the UK government initiated the National Tutoring Programme (NTP) to alleviate the detrimental effects of the Covid-19 lockdown on education. Subsidized one-to-one tutoring was extended to students from economically disadvantaged families, with the government covering 60% of the expenses and schools shouldering the remainder. According to research by the Sutton Trust (2023), the NTP played a role in lessening the gap in tutoring accessibility between higher and lower income households. Initially, higher income households were 15% more likely to access private

tutoring, but this discrepancy narrowed to just 1% with the inclusion of NTP-funded tutoring. The advantages of increased access to one-to-one or small group tuition have been widely acknowledged, with school staff affirming that the NTP effectively addressed students' learning needs while aligning with the curriculum. Despite its positive impact on student achievement and progress, the sustainability of initiatives like the NTP depends on their cost-effectiveness. While the NTP is scheduled to conclude in 2024 due to budgetary constraints, the potential for AI to lower costs and ensure long-term accessibility to personalized learning is promising. If implemented securely and responsibly, AI has the potential to revolutionize education by rendering personalized learning financially sustainable and universally accessible.

AI-Driven Personalized Learning Applications

The utilization of AI in publicly funded tutoring programs presents a compelling advantage in terms of cost reduction. Khanmigo, a prominent digital tutoring platform, offers its services for just \$4 per month per student as a non-profit organization, in stark contrast to private tutoring rates averaging around \$30 per student for just one hour. This nominal fee could be feasibly covered by the government, schools, or even budget-conscious parents. On a broader scale, this could result in substantial savings for governments and educational institutions while still affording students personalized learning support through digital tutoring. While AI tutor platforms cannot replace the unique value of human tutors, they can nonetheless offer a relatively comprehensive and personalized learning experience. For instance, platforms like Khanmigo and Cognii provide step-by-step explanations of school subjects, offer individualized feedback on students' answers to questions, and support literacy through various dialogue-based activities such as word games, debates, and collaborative story-writing.

According to Paul Henninger, head of UK Connected Technology and Global Lighthouse, AI tutoring platforms like these will have a particularly transformative impact on low achievers, providing them with readily available feedback whenever needed. Other AI tutoring applications like Duolingo and MATHai offer free or low-cost learning support for specific academic skills, such as language learning and numeracy, respectively. These specialized applications can be especially beneficial for disadvantaged students struggling with specific subjects, yet not meeting the criteria for subsidized tutoring due to their overall academic achievement. Moreover, they present opportunities for disadvantaged students to broaden their educational horizons by accessing subjects not typically taught in school, such as minority languages. Historically, access to non-mainstream subjects has been a privilege reserved for students from affluent families who can afford subject-specific private tutoring or extracurricular activities.

Adaptive learning systems, powered by AI, have the capacity to analyze students' performance, strengths, and weaknesses to provide tailored learning experiences. Virtual tutors, driven by AI, offer individualized education to students, catering to their unique learning styles and emotional requirements (Jonnalagadda et al., 2023; Mahfood et al., 2023). AI technology enables the personalization of learning by assessing individual strengths and limitations, forecasting future performance, tracking knowledge states, and examining past interactions and navigation patterns. This facilitates the customization of educational experiences to suit each student's distinct needs while also predicting their future academic performance. In a study by Long et al. (2022), knowledge tracing was presented as a method to estimate students' knowledge states by predicting their likelihood of correctly answering questions,

crucial for online learning platforms. The study introduced Collaborative Knowledge Tracing (CoKT), leveraging inter-student information to enhance knowledge tracing accuracy. AI interventions, such as personalized feedback systems based on deep learning Transformer models (Kulshreshtha et al., 2022) or AI-powered tutoring platforms like Chrome's Galileo or Khanmigo, have been shown to enhance student engagement, motivation, and retention (Bhutoria, 2022). These personalized feedback systems employ cause-effect analysis and text similarity-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) Transformer models to identify correct, incorrect, or missing components in student responses and guide them towards correct answers through natural language interactions. According to a recent investigation (St-Hilaire et al., 2022), learning outcomes were notably superior for users of Korbit, a Canadian AI-driven educational platform. Korbit employs machine learning algorithms to tailor the learning experience to individual students, surpassing the outcomes observed with platforms lacking personalized feedback mechanisms. Moreover, the automation of labour-intensive administrative duties such as assessment, grading, and instructional planning can further enhance learning outcomes. This automation liberates educators to concentrate on direct engagement with students and the implementation of effective teaching methodologies.

Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS)

In general, AI-driven tutoring assistance, although not yet at par with human tutoring, has the potential to alleviate tutors' workload by automating and gamifying simpler and foundational learning tasks. This shift may redefine the role of human tutors, emphasizing soft skills like critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving. Consequently, there might be a reduced necessity for one-on-one tutoring sessions with students. Integrating AI tutoring platforms could serve as a pivotal strategy for schools to decrease the overall cost of tutoring per student and ensure the financial sustainability of publicly funded initiatives such as the National Tutoring Programme (NTP).

Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) represent a paradigm shift in educational technology, harnessing the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to deliver personalized and adaptive learning experiences. The evolution of ITS can be traced back to the early days of computer-based instruction, where rule-based systems provided rudimentary forms of tutoring. Over time, advancements in AI technologies, including machine learning, natural language processing, and cognitive modelling, have fuelled the development of more sophisticated ITS platforms capable of modelling learner behaviour, adapting instruction, and providing intelligent feedback. AI techniques play a pivotal role in the functioning of ITS, enabling personalized instruction, adaptive learning pathways, and intelligent tutoring interventions. Machine learning algorithms, such as neural networks and decision trees, analyse student data to infer knowledge states, predict learning trajectories, and optimize instructional strategies. Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms facilitate conversational interactions between students and virtual tutors, enabling intelligent feedback and dialogue-based learning experiences. Key components of AI-based ITS include knowledge representation, student modelling, and pedagogical strategies. Knowledge representation techniques, such as semantic networks and ontologies, encode domain knowledge and learner profiles to support personalized instruction. Student modelling algorithms track learner progress, preferences, and performance data to adapt instruction in real-time. Pedagogical strategies encompass a range of AI-driven interventions, including

adaptive feedback, scaffolded support, and interactive simulations, tailored to individual learner needs.

AI-Enabled ITS Applications

Mousavinasab and colleagues (2021) conducted an examination of the characteristics of Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs) across diverse educational domains. Predominantly, computer sciences (37.73%) represented the educational fields within these ITSs. Notably, action-condition rule-based reasoning, data mining, and Bayesian network techniques were frequently employed, with frequencies of 33.96%, 22.64%, and 20.75% respectively. These methodologies empower ITSs to furnish adaptive guidance and instruction, assess learners, refine learner models, and categorize or group learners. Kochmar et al (2022) proposed a machine learning-based strategy for generating personalized feedback automatically, catering to individual student requirements without necessitating expert intervention or predefined rules. By leveraging cutting-edge machine learning and natural language processing techniques, personalized feedback, including hints and Wikipedia-based explanations, was provided to students, resulting in enhanced success rates in exercise completion. AlShaikh and Hewahi (2021) conducted a thorough review of prior ITS research utilizing various AI and Machine Learning (ML) techniques, outlining current research endeavours, challenges, and prospects. Notably, emphasis was placed on Reinforcement Learning (RL), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), clustering, Bayesian Network (BN), and Fuzzy Logic (FL) approaches. Alam (2023) investigated the integration of advanced technologies into education to enhance student learning experiences and curriculum delivery. Adaptive learning, facilitated by algorithms analyzing student performance data to tailor content and pedagogy, was highlighted as a key area. Lu et al (2021) introduced RadarMath, an innovative intelligent tutoring system designed to support personalized learning in math education through services such as automatic grading and tailored learning guidance. The system showcased the application of relevant AI techniques in modern ITSs. Additionally, Kochmar et al (2022) explored the automatic generation of feedback in a large-scale ITS, emphasizing how personalized feedback contributes to improved student performance outcomes.

Automated Student Assessment

This is another major area of AI application in education. AI has the potential of automating the repetitive and tedious tasks of evaluating and assessing student performance by providing fast, unbiased, and real-time personalised feedback. Utilizing machine learning techniques and Natural Language Processing (NLP), AI has the capability to analyse a wide range of student work, spanning from basic multiple-choice questions to complex written assignments and even verbal responses. Assessment tools powered by AI have the capacity to assess intricate tasks like essays and problem-solving exercises, alleviating the workload of educators while enhancing the precision and uniformity of grading (Vittorini *et al*, 2021). This applicability ensures more objectivity in assessment and evaluation thereby eliminating human bias and errors whilst allowing instructors/teachers to focus on other areas of learning. AI-based Automated assessment tools have the capability to discern patterns in students' performance, pinpointing areas where they might benefit from extra support or resources. This functionality empowers educators to base their decisions on data and craft tailored interventions tailored to each student's unique learning requirements. By furnishing immediate feedback and comprehensive insights into students' strengths and areas needing improvement, this personalized approach to evaluation can enhance learning outcomes and foster a more immersive educational environment for students.

Ercikan and McCaffrey (2022) introduced a framework grounded in evidence-centered design principles, aimed at crafting assessments that harmonize conceptualization, scoring, and subsequent interpretation and application, with a particular emphasis on exploring the merits and constraints of AI-based scoring. We propose guidelines for delineating construct, task, and evidence models to inform task and assessment construction, thus optimizing the deployment of AI-based automated scoring systems for constructed response items and bolstering the validity of score inferences and applications. Research suggests that text-based assessments foster deeper learning engagement compared to multiple-choice formats (Gao et al., 2024). Moreover, short-answer questions have exhibited heightened reliability and validity compared to single-best-answer formats, with respondents perceiving them as more authentic (Sam et al., 2018). Text-based Automated Assessment Systems (TBAAS) hold promise in nurturing conceptual thinking through writing and feedback, potentially enhancing students' cognitive development.

Significant advancements have been witnessed in the education sector over recent years, with educational institutions increasingly transitioning to online platforms to expand resources available to students. The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated this shift, offering students greater flexibility to learn and progress at their own pace. Correspondingly, the demand for online proctoring services, including AI-based proctoring systems (referred to as AIPS), has surged. Such systems, alongside conventional online proctoring systems (OPS), utilize digital tools to uphold examination integrity. However, the collection of sensitive data by these systems has raised apprehensions among students, necessitating a comprehensive consideration of psychological, cultural, and technological factors in AIPS development. A comprehensive review of existing AI and non-AI-based proctoring systems was conducted (Nigam *et al*, 2021) addressing four critical areas: the architectural framework of AIPS, parameters pertinent to AIPS development, prevailing trends and challenges, and prospects of AIPS. Evaluating whether the benefits of online proctoring technologies outweigh the associated risks remains a complex endeavour. Presently, ethical deliberations and considerations of potential benefits necessitate a meticulous balancing act. This study also highlights emerging technologies poised to significantly impact online education and OPS in the foreseeable future. Although AI can greatly enhance student learning, most of its applications predominantly center on cost-saving measures by minimizing manual assessment requirements. It is crucial to consider the viewpoints of both teachers and students regarding this form of automation. Braun *et al* (2023) conducted surveys to ascertain their perspectives on AI-supported assessment and to delineate the circumstances under which they would embrace such technology. The findings indicate that a significant proportion of students (80% and above) are amenable to AI-supported assessment under specific conditions. Notably, they emphasize the importance of human involvement in the assessment process.

Teacher-Student Collaboration

AI has the capability of playing a pivotal role in fostering collaboration between educators and students, thereby enriching the learning journey. In-class assessments and immediate feedback mechanisms enable educators to make timely adjustments during lessons. Additionally, AI can alert educators to students who may be encountering difficulties and suggest potential solutions. Serving as a collaborative partner, AI aids in brainstorming effective strategies to bolster student learning. Various collaboration tools find application in educational settings. Lee and colleagues

(2021) investigated the integration of AI-enhanced collaborative inquiry learning into upper elementary school classrooms (ages 8 to 11) through the utilization of game-based learning approaches. Their study introduces the design of PrimaryAI, a game-based learning platform tailored to facilitate immersive problem-solving activities rooted in life sciences within upper elementary classrooms.

In distance learning, the inability to share the same physical space with students presents challenges for educators. In the constructivist perspective of education, significant teacher-student interaction is crucial, and the inability to observe students' academic progress is undesirable. In addressing the difficulties educators face in gauging students' knowledge levels, Kim *et al* (2021) presented a Student Knowledge Prediction Framework which models and elucidates students' knowledge states, enabling educators to better understand their mastery levels of various concepts over time. Integrated into an e-learning platform, this framework provides automated feedback to facilitate the instructional process. Zhan *et al* (2021) investigated the interaction dynamics between teachers and students in both smart classrooms (SC) and traditional multimedia classrooms (TMC). Their objective was to juxtapose the interaction dynamics between these two classroom environments and underscore any deficiencies in traditional in-person instruction. The study outcomes unveiled that in synchronous online learning environments, there was a discernible uptick in teacher-student interactions, coupled with a heightened emphasis on collaborative group endeavours. Moreover, the implementation of intelligent classrooms facilitated enhanced teacher-student engagement, characterized by increased depth and efficiency. Notably, a transition in teaching methodology from the conventional question-and-answer format in traditional classroom settings to inquiry-based and collaborative learning in smart classrooms was evident. Sun and colleagues (2021) proposed a model termed Collaborative Teacher-Student Learning via Multiple Knowledge Transfer (CTSL-MKT), designed to foster both independent and collaborative learning. This approach enables multiple students to acquire knowledge through individual experiences and relational instances collaboratively. Through self-distillation, students learn from their own experiences, while also guiding each other through online distillation. Experimental trials and ablation studies conducted on four image datasets indicate that the CTSL-MKT model outperforms existing knowledge distillation methods significantly. Additionally, King *et al.* (2022) assessed the efficacy of delivering behavioural skills training via an automated virtual reality (VR) simulation employing artificial intelligence to enhance the implementation of a nondirective mathematical questioning strategy. The outcomes illustrate the potential of AI-augmented VR to provide effective, evidence-based training with minimal instructor oversight.

Methodology

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the potential influence of AI on educational equity through an examination of existing literature in the field. Employing a comprehensive scoping review methodology, this research conducts a thematic analysis of current literature concerning the ramifications of AI on educational equity within the context of the United Kingdom.

Figure 1. PRISMA Data Collection and Processing Methodology

Figure 1 illustrates the PRISMA Data Collection and Processing methodology, delineating the steps undertaken throughout the data collection and review process. The literature exploration spans a six-year period from 2019 to 2024, with a primary focus on academic and scholarly publications, drawing from databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar. The study unfolds across five stages: (1) formulation of research question(s), (2) identification of pertinent publications, (3) selection of relevant papers, (4) organization of data, and (5) synthesis and presentation of findings.

In the initial stage, the research questions explored are as follows:

Research Question 1: What is the impact of AI on educational equity?

Research Question 2: What are the various application domains of AI in Educational system?

The subsequent stage involved discerning relevant studies. To prioritize recent research, the database search is confined to the preceding six years (2019 to 2024), specifically targeting academic publications within this timeframe. During the third stage, a meticulous selection process was enacted to minimize bias. The criteria for inclusion encompassed studies that were (a) written in English, (b) peer-reviewed publications, (c) reports, (d) op-eds, and (e) published between 2019 and April 2024. A total of 100 papers were initially retrieved, and after meticulous analysis adhering to the PRISMA Statement guidelines, 40 papers met the inclusion criteria (refer to Table 1).

Table 1. Selected Publications Showing AI Application Area and Impact Evaluation

S/N	Paper	Major Application area(s)	Evaluates Impact of AI on educational Equity
1	Pedro <i>et al</i> (2019)	Personalised learning, Learning outcome, Intelligent tutoring systems, Teacher-Student Collaboration	Yes
2	Terzopoulos & Satratzemi (2019)	Intelligent Tutoring System	No
3	Webber <i>et al</i> (2019)	Learning outcome	No
4	Tafazoli <i>et al</i> (2019)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning	No
5	Alsobhi & Alyoubi. (2019)	Personalised Learning	No
6	Marcinkowski <i>et al</i> (2020)	-	No
7	Cheddadi & Bouache (2021)	Learning outcome, Automated Assessment	Yes
8	Miao <i>et al</i> (2021)	Intelligent Tutoring Systems, Automated Assessment, Personalised Learning	Yes
9	Borenstein & Howard. (2021)	Automated Assessment	No
10	Kamalov <i>et al</i> (2021)	Automated Assessment	No
11	Miao <i>et al</i> (2021)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Automated Assessment	No
12	Hoppe <i>et al</i> (2021)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning, Automated Assessment	No
13	Bernard <i>et al</i> (2021)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Automated Assessment	No
14	Zhang & Cao (2021)	Personalised Learning, Learning outcome, Intelligent Tutoring System	No
15	Chine <i>et al</i> (2022)	Personalised Learning	Yes
16	Holstein & Doroudi (2022)	-	Yes
17	Stephenson & Harvey (2022)	Automated Assessment	Yes
18	Roscoe <i>et al</i> (2022)	Personalised learning, Learning outcome, Automated Assessment, Teacher-Student Collaboration	Yes
19	Tanveer <i>et al</i> (2022)	-	Partly
20	Kulshreshtha <i>et al</i> (2022)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised Learning	No
21	St-Hilaire <i>et al</i> (2022)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised Learning, Learning outcome	No
22	Liu <i>et al</i> (2022)	Personalised learning, Automated Assessment	No
23	Fang <i>et al</i> (2022)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning, Learning outcome, Automated Assessment	No
24	Kochmar <i>et al</i> (2022)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning, Learning outcome	No
25	Judijanto <i>et al</i> (2022)	Learning outcome, Personalised learning,	Partly
26	Nuary <i>et al</i> (2022)	Personalised learning	Partly
27	Tanga & Chen (2023)	Personalised learning	No
28	Nguyen <i>et al</i> (2023)	-	No

29	Qadir (2023)	Personalised learning, Intelligent Tutoring System	Partly
30	Chan & Tsi (2023)	Teacher – Student Collaboration	No
31	Chen <i>et al</i> (2023)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning	No
32	Elkins <i>et al</i> (2023)	Automated Assessment	No
33	Hu <i>et al</i> (2023)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised learning	No
34	Lodge <i>et al</i> (2023)	Personalised learning, Automated Assessment	No
35	Perkins (2023)	Automated Assessment, Personalised learning	No
36	Rasul <i>et al</i> (2023)	Adaptive learning, Personalised learning, Learning outcome, Automated Assessment	Partly
37	Zaman (2023).	Personalised learning, Learning outcome	No
38	Rane <i>et al</i> (2023)	Intelligent Tutoring System, Personalised Learning, Adaptive learning, Learning outcome, Teacher-Student Collaboration	Partly
39	Sappaile <i>et al</i> (2024)	Learning outcome, Personalised learning	No
40	Roshanaei (2024)	-	Yes

In the fourth stage, data from the 40 selected studies are charted in Table 1 and thematic analysis is used to identify themes/application areas. The last stage presents and summarizes our results and findings for future research.

Results and Findings

The findings of the study indicate that most of the selected research, following the PRISMA Methodology and application of exclusion and inclusion criteria, fall within the timeframe of 2019 to 2024 (refer to Table 1). The distribution of research is as shown in Figure 2: 2019 (12.5%), 2020 (2.5%), 2021 (20%), 2022 (30%), 2023 (30%) and 2024 (5%).

Figure 2. Distribution of Research Papers by Year

We could see that the lowest distribution witnessed in 2024 is since this study is limited up till April 2024, however, the years 2022 and 2023 recorded highest percentages of research on AI application and impact on educational equity.

Figure 3. Distribution Percentage of AI application areas in Education by Selected Papers

The study also shows that 62.5% of the research presented AI applications in Personalised learning experience, while 40% of the papers presented AI-based intelligent tutoring systems (as shown in Figure 3). Further results show that 35% of the papers presented AI-based automated assessment/testing applications, 32.5% of the papers focussed on AI-enabled applications in improving educational learning outcomes while 10% of the papers dwelled on teacher-student collaboration. Five of the papers did not explicitly understudy any of the aforementioned AI application areas in education, thus the reason for the “- “sign. From figure 4, it is pertinent to note that only 8 out of the 40 selected research publications (i.e. 20%) evaluated the potential impact of AI-based application in educational equity while 6 out of the 40 selected publications (15%) stressed on the need for the impact of AI-enabled applications on achieving educational equity to be addressed in future work. The study shows that not so much have been done in evaluating the impact of AI applications in addressing the socio-economic, ethnic/racial disparities as regards educational equity.

Figure 4. Percentage of Selected Papers that Evaluates the Impact of AI on Educational Equity

This brings to bear the need for a collective effort between private sector, research institutions, global tech community and policy makers in fostering an inclusive and sustainable AI deployment in education system. In the context of UK education, bridging the rural-urban divide represents a critical imperative for fostering equitable access to quality learning opportunities. Leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies presents a promising avenue for addressing this challenge. AI-enabled tools and platforms have demonstrated their potential to support remote learning, offering personalized instruction, adaptive feedback, and interactive learning experiences. By harnessing AI, educators can overcome geographical barriers and deliver high-quality education to students in rural areas, thereby narrowing the gap in educational opportunities between rural and urban communities. Initiatives aimed at connecting rural schools with quality educational resources play a pivotal role in advancing this agenda. Through partnerships with government agencies, educational institutions, and technology providers, initiatives such as broadband expansion projects, mobile learning initiatives, and virtual classroom programs are extending access to educational resources and infrastructure in rural areas. Additionally, collaborative efforts between rural and urban schools, facilitated by AI-powered platforms, promote knowledge sharing, resource pooling, and professional development opportunities for educators.

Recommendations

Investing more in AI-driven assistive technologies, such as speech recognition systems, text-to-speech converters, and image recognition software, is imperative to empower students with disabilities to access educational content in diverse formats. These advancements serve to bridge the gap in special educational needs and disabilities (SEND). Communication aids, like speech-generating devices and augmented reality (AR) tools, enabled by AI, aid students with speech and language disorders, autism spectrum disorder (ASD), and other communication difficulties. Through the utilization of natural language processing (NLP) algorithms and machine learning

techniques, these tools enhance both expressive and receptive communication skills, fostering confident self-expression and meaningful learning experiences.

The adoption of these inclusive technologies can be facilitated through the following policies and practices:

1. **Legislative Frameworks:** Government policies such as the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) in the United States and the Equality Act in the United Kingdom mandate equal access to education and prohibit discrimination against individuals with disabilities. These regulations establish legal obligations for educational institutions to ensure accessibility and inclusion across physical and digital learning environments, thereby promoting the adoption of inclusive technologies.
2. **Universal Design for Learning (UDL):** The Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework advocates for the creation of educational materials and settings that are accessible to all students, including those with disabilities. By embracing principles of flexibility, multiple representation methods, engagement strategies, and varied expression channels, UDL fosters the development of inclusive teaching methods and encourages the integration of AI-driven technologies to cater to diverse learner needs.
3. **Collaborative Partnerships:** Collaborative efforts between educational institutions, technology providers, disability advocacy groups, and community stakeholders facilitate the design and implementation of inclusive technologies. Through joint endeavours to identify barriers, share expertise, and co-create innovative solutions, stakeholders can harness the transformative potential of AI to advance accessibility and inclusivity in education.
4. **Professional Development and Training:** Educator training and professional development initiatives are pivotal in promoting awareness, knowledge, and proficiency in inclusive teaching practices and the effective utilization of AI-enhanced technologies. By offering educators training on accessibility standards, assistive technologies, and inclusive instructional strategies, educational institutions empower teachers to establish inclusive learning environments that accommodate the diverse needs of all students.

Ethical Considerations and Sustainable AI deployment in Education

With the increasing integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in education, it becomes crucial to address both the environmental impact and ethical considerations associated with AI deployment. Ethical considerations play a pivotal role in ensuring that AI deployment in education adheres to principles of fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy. Ethical frameworks offer guidance for responsible AI development and deployment, tackling issues like bias, discrimination, algorithmic transparency, data privacy, and accountability for AI-generated outcomes. By adhering to ethical guidelines, educational institutions can foster trust among stakeholders and ensure that AI deployment respects the rights and dignity of students, educators, and other involved parties. Notably, ethical frameworks provide a comprehensive set of principles and guidelines for the responsible deployment of AI in education, covering aspects such as fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy. For instance, initiatives like the UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education (IITE) and the International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) have formulated ethical guidelines for AI deployment in education, emphasizing student

privacy, data security, and equitable access to AI-powered educational resources. By adhering to these frameworks, educational institutions can uphold ethical standards and promote the well-being of all stakeholders.

Sustainable AI infrastructure in education encompasses several essential components, including energy-efficient hardware, data center optimization, and the integration of renewable energy sources. Energy-efficient hardware, such as low-power processors and servers, helps reduce the energy consumption of AI systems while maintaining performance. Data center optimization strategies, like virtualization and workload consolidation, maximize resource utilization and minimize environmental impact. Furthermore, the integration of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power into educational institutions' infrastructure contributes to reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainability. Addressing both the environmental and ethical implications of AI deployment in education necessitates a holistic approach that encompasses sustainable infrastructure solutions and adherence to ethical frameworks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has provided an insightful review of the current educational landscape in the UK, highlighting significant disparities in education equity and the digital divide. Through a comprehensive scoping review of relevant literature spanning from 2019 to April 2024, we assessed the impact of AI tools on educational equity in the UK. Out of 100 publications identified through the PRISMA methodology, 40 were selected for detailed analysis. Our findings revealed a notable gap in research, with only approximately 20% of the reviewed literature dedicated to investigating the potential impact of AI deployment on educational equity in the UK. This underscores the need for a more deliberate and focused approach to evaluating the effectiveness of AI-enabled applications in addressing educational equity issues.

Moreover, through thematic analysis, we observed that the majority of works on AI-based applications in addressing educational equity primarily centered on personalized learning (approximately 62.5%) and intelligent tutoring systems (40%). While these areas show promise in leveraging AI to enhance educational equity, there remains a need for further exploration and diversification of research efforts. Moving forward, it is imperative for researchers, policymakers, and educators to collaborate and prioritize initiatives aimed at harnessing the full potential of AI technologies to promote equitable access to education for all students in the UK.

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